

ATTITUDE AND AWARENESS TOWARDS CYBER CRIME AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

Undoubtedly, evolution of technology makes each one of us advanced in every sphere of life. But these technologies, specially internet increases cybercrime. This paper highlights serious concerns among prospective teacher's attitude and awareness towards cyber Crime. The objectives of the study is to investigate the attitude and awareness of prospective teachers and to find significant difference in their attitude and awareness in relation to gender and time spent on social media. The study was conducted on 186 prospective teachers from the city of Patna. The Self-constructed and validated Cyber Crime Attitude Scale and Cyber Crime Awareness Scale have been used for the study.

The results indicate that only 15.59% of prospective teachers have positive attitude and 18.82% have high awareness. Most of the prospective teachers have neutral and average level of awareness. The result declared that there is a significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards cybercrime and the time spent on social media.

Keywords : Cyber Crime, Prospective teachers, Internet, Attitude and Awareness

INTRODUCTION

Cyber Crime is known as offence that is related to the use of Internet. Nowadays everybody's life depends upon social media. Social networking, online shopping, storing data, gaming, online studying, online jobs, every possible thing that man can think of can be done through the medium of internet. Extensive use of internet makes the way of cyber crime easier. Cyber-crimes are committed in different forms. A few years back, there was a lack of awareness about the Cyber Crimes. In the matters of Cyber Crimes, India is also not far behind the other countries where the rate of incidence of Cyber Crimes is also increasing.

In a report published by the National Crime Records Bureau report (NCRB 2011), the incidence of cybercrimes under the IT Act has increased by 85.4% in the year 2011 as compared to 2010 in India, whereas the increase in incidence of the crime under IPC is by 18.5% as compared to the year 2010.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Bhutia (2019) conducted a study on Cyber Crime Awareness among Student-Teacher of B.Ed. in Relation to Internate Usage. The use of technology in the field of education has become a blessing to the modern educational system. The study used descriptive survey method. The study found that the locale and having computer have impact on Cyber Crime awareness. There is a relation between the browsing period and Cyber Crime awareness among student teacher of shilong.

Rajender and others (2017) conducted a study on Cyber Crime Awareness among B.Ed. and M.Ed. students of Sirsa district. Cyber Crime is a Social and monetary wonder and is as old as the human culture. So Cyber Crime or offence is "alegitimate wrong that can be trailed by criminal procedures which may come about into discipline.

Josephine & Sudarshan (2016) worked on Cyber Crime Awareness Among B.Ed., Student Teachers. The findings of the study show that there exist significant difference in CyberCrime awareness of B.Ed. Students with respect to sex, locality, knowledge of computer.

Goel (2014) has done a study on awareness among B.Ed. teacher trainees towards Cyber Crime. The present study aims to find out the Cyber Crime awareness among B.Ed. teacher trainees. The study reveals that there is no significant different towards Cyber Crime awareness among boys and girls. There is a significant difference towards Cyber Crime awareness among urban boys and girls, science and art boys and girls.

Singaravelu, Pillai (2014) worked on B.Ed. Students Awareness on Cyber Crime in Perambalur District. The finding of the study shows that most B.Ed. students are in low level of awareness on cyber forums. So, it is suggested that B.Ed. students should balance the cyber technology.

Types of Cyber Crime

Cyber Crime is possible, where electronic communication takes place. Due to the expansion of internet, various Cyber Crime comes forward, mainly are as follows :

i. Digital Forgery :

Forgery is creation of documents which one knows is not genuine and yet projects the same as if it is genuine. Digital forgery implies making use of digital technology to forge a document.

ii. Cyber Pornography :

Pornography literally means, Writings, 'pictures or films designed to be sexually exciting". Developing, distributing and propagating the same over the internet is termed as cyber pornography. This would include pornographic web sites, pornographic magazines produced using computers to publish and print the material and the internet to download

and transmit pornographic pictures etc. In recent times, there have been innumerable instances of promotion of pornography using computers. Information technology has made it much easier.

iii. Cyber Stalking/Harassment :

Cyber stalking is an electronic extension of stalking. The electronic medium is used to pursue, harass or contact another in an unsolicited fashion. The term is used to refer to the use of the internet, e-mail or other electronic communication devices to stalk another person. Stalking generally involves harassing or threatening behaviour that an individual engages in repeatedly, such as following a person, appearing at a person's home or place of business, making harassing phone calls.

iv. Online Sale of Illegal Articles :

The sale of illegal articles on the Internet is also one of those computer crimes where the computer is merely a tool to commit the crime. In December 2004, the CEO of Baze.com was arrested in connection with sale of a CD with objectionable material on the website.

v. E-mail Spoofing :

E-mail spoofing is electronic disguising. A spoofed e-mail is one that appears to originate from one source but has been sent from another source. It is the process of electronically covering one's electronic communication in the name of another.

vi. Credit Card Fraud :

Credit card fraud, as the name suggests, involves misusing someone else's credit cards for one's own benefit. This risk of credit card fraud increased especially after the advent of e-commerce. People purchase products online through their credit cards. The websites offering products for purchase require the credit card details of the online buyers so that the price can be credited to the Card. In the process, the details of the credit cards are stored on the server of the online retailer. If one is able to access the servers containing the credit cards details of the online consumer, it is easy to collect those details and then use for one's own benefit in online transactions.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Today all the countries look like a global village because of the uses of internet. Online shopping, gaming, digital learning are not possible without internet. The cases of Cyber Crime increase every day. But it is also found that the people are not aware of the consequences of wrong use of internet. Cyberbullying and cyberstalking harassment by computer are very common type of Cyber Crime. In this pandemic condition when teaching learning is based on computer, therefore it becomes a part of the study that students and teachers both are aware of the activities related to Cyber Crime. In this context, the investigator presents the prospective teachers' attitude and their awareness regarding Cyber Crime. Online teaching is a technology based teaching so it is a basic requirement that every prospective teacher must be aware of the pros and cons of online teaching activity.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is very essential to be aware of Cyber Crime. Our students are also affected by Cyber Crime and their awareness is very low. In this situation it is essential to make them aware of it. Hence, the role of teachers become crucial and it is possible when teacher training colleges come forward. They bear the responsibility of making aware the prospective teachers as a part of curriculum. In this study the investigator tries to explore the attitude and awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

- **CYBER CRIME**
Criminal activities carried out by means of computers or the internet.
- **PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS**
Teacher candidates who are enrolled in a teacher education program at secondary level. They are also known as B.Ed. Trainees.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- i. To study the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime.
- ii. To study the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime.
- iii. To find the significant difference in the attitude and awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime on the basis of gender.
- iv. To find the significant difference in the attitude and awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time they use for social media.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- i. There is no significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime on the basis of gender.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time they use for social media.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime on the basis of gender.
- iv. There is no significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time they use for social media.

TOOL USED FOR THE STUDY

Tools used for the present study are as follows :

1. Self constructed and validated Cyber Crime Attitude Scale
2. Cyber Crime Awareness Scale developed by Dr. S. Rajeshker (CCAS)

METHOD USED

The study is conducted by online survey. Data has been collected by google form.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

For the present study, all the prospective teachers from

teachers training colleges from city of Patna have been taken as the population of the study.

SAMPLE

The sample comprises of 186 randomly selected prospective teachers of city of Patna.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- i. The study is limited to 186 prospective teachers.
- ii. The study is limited to only prospective teachers.
- iii. The study is limited to the city of Patna.

DATA ANALYSIS

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Table no. 01

Attitude of Prospective Teachers on CyberCrime

Cyber Crime	Positive Attitude	Neutral	Negative Attitude	Total
Number	29	133	24	186
Percentage	15.60%	71.50%	12.90%	100%

It is inferred from table no. 01 that 15.59% prospective teachers have positive attitude, 71.50% have neutral and 12.90% have negative attitude towards Cyber Crime.

Table No. - 2

Awareness of Perspective teachers towards Cyber Crime

Cyber Crime	High Awareness	Average Awareness	Low Awareness	Total
Number	35	124	27	186
Percentage (%)	18.82%	66.66%	14.52%	100%

It is inferred from table no. 02 that 18.82% prospective teachers have high awareness 66.66% have average and 14.52% have low awareness towards Cyber Crime.

Table No. - 3
Gender wise attitude of perspective teachers towards Cyber Crime

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remark
Male	61	118.82	10.42	1.59	N.S.
Female	125	116.57	8.23		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from table no. 3 that the t-value (1.47) of prospective teachers towards cyber crime is less than the table value (1.96). Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime.

Hypothesis no. 2 : There is no significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time they used for social media.

Table No. - 4
Attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime on the basis of time spent on social media

Time spent for social media	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remark
<5 hours	159	118.05	8.59	2.38	S
>5 hours	27	112.96	10.52		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from table no. 3 that the t-value (2.38) of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime is more than the table value (1.96). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time

that they used for social media. The mean score shows that prospective teachers who spent less than 5 hours on social media have a better attitude towards Cyber Crime rather than those who spent more than 5 hours.

Table no. 5

Genderwise awareness of perspective teachers towards Cyber Crime

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remark
Male	61	124.77	10.44	9.57	S
Female	125	125.62	8.88		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from table no. 5 that the t-value (9.57) of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime is more than the table value (1.96). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. And it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime. The mean score shows that the females are more aware than males towards Cyber Crime.

Table no. 6

Awareness of perspective teachers towards Cyber Crime on the basis of time spent on social media

Time spent for social media	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remark
<5 hours	159	126.20	9.34	3.39	S
>5 hours	27	120.25	8.34		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from table no. 6 that the t-value (3.39) of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime is more than the table value (1.96). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. And it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the awareness of prospective

teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time that they used for social media. The mean score shows who spent less than 5 hours on social media have a more awareness towards Cyber Crime rather than those who spent more than 5 hours on social media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher has conducted a study on the attitude and awareness towards Cyber Crime on prospective teachers of B.Ed.

- Percentage analysis results indicate prospective teacher's attitude and awareness both are not at appropriate level. 15.59% have positive attitude and 18.82% have high awareness. Most of them have neutral and average level of awareness. It reveals that there is essential need to make these teachers aware towards Cyber Crime. Because of pandemic, mostly classes are going on online mode, therefore cyber behaviors must be learned.
- From table no. 2 it can be inferred that 18.82% prospective teachers have high awareness, 66.66% have average and 14.52% have low awareness towards Cyber Crime. This shows that most of the prospective teachers are having average level of awareness about Cyber Crime.
- Table no. 3 indicates that there is no significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime. Here, it can be concluded that both the male and female teachers have similar set of thinking regarding Cyber Crime. In the study Cyber Crime does not create any differences in the attitude among prospective teachers.
- Table no. 4 shows that there is a significant difference in the attitude of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based on time that they used for social media. The calculated mean scores show that the prospective teachers who spent less than 5 hours on social media have a better attitude towards Cyber Crime.
- Table no. 5 shows that there is a significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime. The calculated mean scores show that females have more awareness towards Cyber Crime with a mean score of 125.62 while their male counterparts scored 124.77.
- Table no. 6 declared that there is a significant difference in the awareness of prospective teachers towards Cyber Crime based

on time that they used for social media. The calculated mean score show that the prospective teachers who spent less than 5 hours on social media have a better attitude towards Cyber Crime.

CONCLUSION

To conclude it can be said that prospective teachers are averagely aware towards Cyber Crime and have developed a positive attitude towards it. It can be said that prospective teachers are more digitally aware of all the various Cyber Crime and both males and females think on the same level where Cyber Crime is concerned. By the various findings it can be said that female prospective teachers are more aware about Cyber Crime than their male counterparts. The study also showed that the prospective teachers who spent less than five hours on social media and internet are more aware about Cyber Crimes.

Suggestions :

- i. Teacher Training colleges must conduct some sort of seminars, workshops and orientation programmes on Cyber Crime, cyber security related issues.
- ii. Prospective teachers are suggested to use unique password for social media.
- iii. They must change their password frequently.
- iv. They should talk freely on Cyber Crime related topics in their peer groups.
- v. Prospective teachers should know about the fake websites.

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